

OPTIMUM PLY LAYUP FOR DELAMINATION RESISTANCE IN LAMINATES WITH A HOLE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to find the optimum stacking sequence to minimize the strain energy release rate (G_I) for free-edge delamination growth in a plate with a circular hole. Approximate closed-form solutions are used to compute the stress and G_I distributions. Using these solutions, the sensitivity of G_I with respect to ply angles is computed and used to formulate a linear programming problem. To render a non-trivial design, constraints on the stiffness are introduced. This approach is applied to a rectangular plate loaded under uniform tension with a hole. The results show that by changing stacking angles, it is possible to reduce the probability of delamination while maintaining the longitudinal and transverse stiffness of the plate.

KEYWORDS: Optimization; Durability; Delamination; Damage Tolerance; Energy Release Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing demand for lightweight structures, composite materials are enjoying greater popularity. In composite structural design, delamination is one of the chief concerns. Classical lamination theory can be used to calculate an initial ply stacking sequence that satisfies stiffness requirements[1]. However, there are several ply layups that will yield approximately the same stiffness yet show a marked improvement in delamination resistance. This becomes especially important in structures with holes.

Strain energy release rate is often a parameter used to characterize the delamination in laminated composites. This parameter has been widely used to estimate the delamination resistance of a laminate with free edges.

The objective of this research is to develop an analytic tool which can be used to

find the optimum ply layup to minimize the strain energy release rate (G_T) for free edge delamination growth in a plate with a circular hole. Final design layups will be rounded to the nearest tenth of a degree to reflect the practical limitations of manufacturing.

2. STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE AROUND A HOLE

For delamination around a hole, one can consider a small element along the hole edge as a free-edged laminate. The position of the element is defined by (R, η) where η is the angular measurement in the cylindrical coordinate system shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Geometry and loading condition for a plate with a hole.

The tangential strain state at the hole edge element can be written[2] as

$$e_{\eta} = \frac{\sigma_0}{E_{\eta}} (1 - 2\cos 2\eta) \tag{1}$$

where E_{η} is the apparent laminate stiffness.

Using this strain distribution, the strain can be assumed to be applied uniformly on a small element at the hole and the strain energy release rate can be calculated using a formula proposed by O'Brien and Raju[3]:

$$G_T = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_0^2 T \left(\frac{E_{LAM} - E^*}{E_{LAM}^2} \right) \tag{2}$$

where T is the total laminate thickness, and the stiffness of the plate before delamination is E_{LAM} and after full delamination, E^* . An instantaneous local layup is determined by subtracting η from each ply angle, θ . Classical laminated plate theory (CLT) [1] can then be used to calculate the apparent laminate stiffness in the tangential direction (E_{η}).

Note that the local layup is a function of position around the hole (η). The tangential stiffness (E_{η}), then, must be recalculated at every position of interest. Recalculating the [ABD] matrix from the ply properties at every location could be very

costly. Instead, the laminate compliance matrix can be transformed for any position around the hole using

$$[a(\eta)] = [T]^T [a(0)] [T] \quad (3)$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & 2sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -2sc \\ -sc & sc & (c^2 - s^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $[a(\eta)]$ is the $[a]$ matrix for a position η , $s = \sin(-\eta)$ and $c = \cos(-\eta)$. By multiplying the terms in the transformation matrix affecting a_{22} , a simple expression for E_η can be found.

$$E_\eta = \frac{1}{T(s^4 a_{11} + 2s^2 c^2 a_{12} + 2s^3 c a_{16} + c^4 a_{22} + 2sc^3 a_{26} + s^2 c^2 a_{66})} \quad (5)$$

Similarly, this technique can also be applied to rotate the two sublaminates $[a^s]$ matrices for calculating E^* . This amounts to building the $[ABD]$ or $[ABD^s]$ matrices only once per interface and transforming them to analyze locations around the hole.

3. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The sensitivity of the strain energy release rate to a change in the design variables can be obtained by taking the partial derivative with respect to the angle of a single ply (θ_i). This yields:

$$\frac{\partial G_T}{\partial \theta_i} = \frac{1}{4} \sigma_o^2 T^2 \left[\left(1 - \frac{2E^*}{E_{LAM}}\right) \frac{\partial a_{22}}{\partial \theta_i} + \left(\frac{a_{22}}{a_{22}^s}\right)^2 \frac{\partial a_{22}^s}{\partial \theta_i} \right] \quad (6)$$

where a_{22}^s is an element of the local sublaminates compliance matrix, $[a^s]$ containing the i^{th} ply, and a_{22} is an element of the local compliance matrix, $[a]$.

The above equation implies that determination of the sensitivity of the strain energy release rate amounts to simply determining the sensitivity of the laminate compliance. In general, determining the compliance sensitivity can be obtained from the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial [abd]}{\partial \theta_i} = -[abd] \left[\frac{\partial [ABD]}{\partial \theta_i} \right] [abd] \quad (7)$$

where $[abd]$ is the inverse of the $[ABD]$ matrix. For a general laminate, they are defined as

$$[ABD] = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad [abd] = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ b & d \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

For a symmetric laminate, equation (8) can be written as

$$[a] = [A]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

which is different from $[a]$ in equation (8). Multiplying terms in equation (7) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial (abd_{22})}{\partial \theta_i} = & - \left(\frac{\rho_{11}}{t_i} \right) [t_i a_{12}^2 + a_{12} b_{21} (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{1}{3} b_{21}^2 (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{12}}{t_i} \right) [2 t_i a_{12} a_{22} + (a_{12} b_{22} + a_{22} b_{21}) (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{2}{3} b_{21} b_{22} (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{16}}{t_i} \right) [2 t_i a_{12} a_{26} + (a_{12} b_{26} + a_{26} b_{21}) (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{2}{3} b_{26} b_{21} (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{22}}{t_i} \right) [t_i a_{22}^2 + a_{22} b_{22} (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{1}{3} b_{22}^2 (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{26}}{t_i} \right) [2 t_i a_{22} a_{26} + (a_{22} b_{26} + a_{26} b_{22}) (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{2}{3} b_{22} b_{26} (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{66}}{t_i} \right) [t_i a_{26}^2 + b_{26} a_{26} (h_i^2 - h_{i-1}^2) + \frac{1}{3} b_{26}^2 (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3)] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $s = \sin\theta$, $c = \cos\theta$,

$$\rho_{jk} = \frac{\partial A_{jk}}{\partial \theta_i} \quad (11)$$

and

$$\rho_{11} = t_i [-4Q_{11}^i c^3 s + 4Q_{22}^i s^3 c + 2(Q_{12}^i + 2Q_{66}^i) (2c^3 s - 2s^3 c)] \quad (12)$$

$$\rho_{22} = t_i [4Q_{11}^i s^3 c - 4Q_{22}^i c^3 s + 2(Q_{12}^i + 2Q_{66}^i) (2c^3 s - 2s^3 c)] \quad (13)$$

$$\rho_{12} = t_i [2(Q_{11}^i + Q_{22}^i - 4Q_{66}^i) (c^3 s - s^3 c) + 4Q_{12}^i (s^3 c - c^3 s)] \quad (14)$$

$$\rho_{66} = t_i [2(Q_{11}^i + Q_{22}^i - 2Q_{12}^i - 2Q_{66}^i) (c^3 s - s^3 c) + 4Q_{66}^i (s^3 c - c^3 s)] \quad (15)$$

$$\rho_{16} = t_i [(Q_{11}^i - Q_{12}^i - 2Q_{66}^i) (c^4 - 3c^2 s^2) - (Q_{22}^i - Q_{12}^i - 2Q_{66}^i) (3s^2 c^2 - s^4)] \quad (16)$$

$$\rho_{26} = t_i [(Q_{11}^i - Q_{12}^i - 2Q_{66}^i) (3c^2 s^2 - s^4) - (Q_{22}^i - Q_{12}^i - 2Q_{66}^i) (c^4 - 3c^2 s^2)] \quad (17)$$

It should be noted that if the laminate or sublaminates is symmetric, the corresponding stiffness or compliance matrix can be used [A] or [a] to replace [ABD] or [abd]. Furthermore, all the b's are equal to zero. Equation (10), hence, can be simplified as

$$\frac{\partial a_{22}}{\partial \theta_i} = -a_{12}^2 \rho_{11} - 2a_{12} a_{22} \rho_{12} - 2a_{12} a_{26} \rho_{16} - a_{22}^2 \rho_{22} - 2a_{22} a_{26} \rho_{26} - a_{26}^2 \rho_{66} \quad (18)$$

It should be mentioned that the a's in the above equation are defined in equation (9).

4. FORMULATION OF OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

The optimum design problem can be stated as follows: Find the stacking sequence, θ_i , to minimize the maximum strain energy release rate at the critical interface ($G_T^{(1)}$) while maintaining the stiffness of the plate. This problem will be solved by sequential linear programming[4]. Let us define x_i to be the orientation angle of the i^{th} ply, and z to be the strain energy release rate at the critical interface and location ($z=G_T^{(1)}$). Then the problem becomes: Find x_i, x_2, \dots, x_i to minimize z subject to the following constraints:

$$G_T^{(k)} \leq z \quad (19)$$

$$\left[\frac{E_x^{n+1} - E_x^o}{E_x^o} \right] \leq \epsilon_x \quad (20)$$

$$\left[\frac{E_y^{n+1} - E_y^o}{E_y^o} \right] \leq \epsilon_y \quad (21)$$

Note that the superscript n represents the current iteration design variables, and k represents the finite number of critical locations investigated. Also, it should be noted that the above optimization problem has a linear objective function. When the constraints are linearized by first order Taylor series, the above problem becomes one of linear programming.

Realizing that these linearized equations are valid for small changes in ply angle only, linear programming problems frequently include move limits. In this problem, the change in angle can be positive or negative:

$$|x_j| \leq \xi \quad (22)$$

where ξ is input by the user (5 degrees was used in the example). After some minor manipulations, the above linear programming problem can be solved using the modified simplex method[5]. In this paper, the IMSL routine ZX3LP is used to solve the linear

programming problem. Since the optimization problem is nonlinear, the above procedure has to be repeated until the solution converges. In this paper, the relative change in ply angles between two successive iterations is used as the convergence criterion. That is, the process converges after the $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ iteration when

$$\left| \frac{\theta_i^n - \theta_i^{n+1}}{\theta_i^n} \right| \leq \epsilon \quad (23)$$

for all ply angles, θ_i .

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A quasi-isotropic laminate of $(0,90,\pm 45)_s$ graphite/epoxy with a hole was used for this study. The material has the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} E_L &= 137.9 \text{ GPa (20.0E6 psi)} & \nu_{LT} &= 0.3 \\ E_T &= 14.5 \text{ GPa (2.1E6 psi)} & \text{ply thickness, } t_i &= 0.125 \text{ mm (.005 in)} \\ G_{LT} &= 5.5 \text{ GPa (0.8E6 psi)} \end{aligned}$$

The laminate is subjected to a uniform strain corresponding to a far-field stress of 6.895 MPa (1000 psi). The strain energy release rate is then investigated. Present results were validated by comparing O'Brien and Raju's results[3] at three interfaces 0/90, 90/+45, and +45/-45. Excellent agreement is obtained as one of the cases shows in Figure 2. The top strain energy release rates are listed in Table 1.

Figure 2. Verification of G_T for 45/-45 interface

Table 1. Top G_T locations for initial design

Interface	η degrees	G_T J/m ² (in-lb/in ²)
midplane interface (-45/-45)	90/270	1.826 (.0104)
	75/255	1.642 (.0094)
	285/105	1.276 (.0073)
(90/45)	255/75	1.253 (.0072)
	105/285	1.253 (.0072)

With this design used as a starting point, optimization was performed to lower the maximum strain energy release rate while maintaining the stiffness (within 2%). A move limit of 5 degrees was enforced the first 5 iterations and then was reduced by 20% after each additional iteration until a floor of 150% of the convergence criteria was hit. For this example, the convergence criteria was set at .1 degree; thus, the move limit remained constant at .18 degrees beyond the 19th iteration.

Figures 3 through 6 show the optimization history. Figure 3 shows the stiffness plotted as a function of the iteration number and Figure 4 plots the ply angle as a function of the iteration. The maximum strain energy release rate is plotted in Figure 5. Notice that the maximum strain energy release rate approaches the final design monotonically. Convergence is reached after 30 iterations and results in a final design which has an 85% reduction in the maximum strain energy release rate. Figure 6 shows the location of the maximum strain energy release rate as the optimization progressed.

Figure 3. Optimization history showing stiffness as a function of iteration

Figure 4. Optimization history showing the ply angle as a function of iteration.

Figure 5. Optimization history showing the maximum G_T as a function of iteration.

Figure 6. Optimization history showing location of maximum G_T as a function of iteration.

The top strain energy release rates for the final design are listed in Table 2. The final strain energy release rate distributions (plotted over the initial design) for all four interfaces are presented in Figures 7 through 10.

Table 2. Top G_T locations for final design

Interface	η degrees	G_T J/m ² (in-lb/in ²)
79/-11	105/285	0.277 (0.00158)
-11/79	105/285	0.275 (0.00157)
79/-11	300/120	0.239 (0.00136)
-11/79	300/120	0.236 (0.00135)
79/-11	90/270	0.172 (0.00098)

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A methodology of determining optimal ply stacking for delamination resistance was presented. A closed form solution was used to approximate the stress distribution around the hole edge in a plate which is uniformly strained. This distribution was applied to an analytic model to predict the strain energy release rate for the hole free edge. Linear programming was then used to evaluate alternate stacking sequences for delamination resistance. An example was demonstrated to determine the ply layup that gives a minimum of the maximum strain energy release rate. A final design was proposed which had a reduction of strain energy release rate by 85%, thus improving markedly the delamination resistance. Increased delamination resistance translates to a longer part life, improved reliability, and, ultimately, lower cost.

Note that work needs to be done on the parameters used to predict delamination. It was conceived that delamination failure is governed by the failure mode which may be dependent on the material system. Work can be concentrated on constraining the components of the total strain energy release rate to its allowable of each individual failure mode. Furthermore, experimental work is required to validate the failure mode and design solution.

Figure 7. Comparison of initial and final G_T distributions for interface between first and second ply.

Figure 8. Comparison of initial and final G_T distributions for interface between second and third ply.

Figure 9. Comparison of initial and final G_T distributions for interface between third and fourth ply.

Figure 10. Comparison of initial and final G_T distributions for midplane interface.

7. LIST OF REFERENCES

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